

BIOTRAILS

Project acronym: BIOTRAILS
Title: Nexus Framework for biodiversity-relevant transformative change
Grant Agreement number: 101082008

PSDM and scenario building

Description: Technical publication
Lead beneficiary: CNR
Document type: R — Document, report
Responsible Authors: Raffaele Giordano, Stefania Santoro (CNR)
Contributions from: KNUST, CIAT, HAPO
Project URL: www.biotrailsproject.eu

Funded by
the European Union

BIOTRAILS Partners	
<p>CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE Piazzale aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma, Italy</p>	
<p>CHAROKOPEIO PANEPISTIMIO Eleftheriou Venizelou 70, 176 71 Athens, Greece</p>	
<p>ADELPHI RESEARCH GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH Alt-Moabit 91, 10559 Berlin, Germany</p>	
<p>WHITE RESEARCH SPRL Avenue de la Toison D'Or 67, 1060 Saint Gilles, Belgium</p>	
<p>STICHTING GLOBAL RESILIENT CITIES NETWORK Korte Hoogstraat 31, 3011 Rotterdam, Netherlands</p>	
<p>DRAXIS ENVIRONMENTAL SA Themistokli Sofouli Str. 54-56, 54655 Thessaloniki, Greece</p>	
<p>EBOS TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED Arch. Makariou III & Mesaorias 1 Office 101, 2322 Nicosia, Cyprus</p>	
<p>CENTRO INTERNACIONAL DE AGRICULTURA TROPICAL Kilometro 17 Recta Cali, 763537 Palmira, Colombia</p>	
<p>HELLENIC AQUACULTURE PRODUCERS ORGANIZATION Leoforos Lavriou 99B, 19002 Paiania, Greece</p>	
<p>KWAME NKURUMAH UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY KUMASI Private Mail Bag, University Post Office, Kumasi Ash, Ghana</p>	
<p>EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH Rämistr. 101, 8092 Zurich, Switzerland</p>	

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	4
1. INTRODUCTION	4
2. PSDM METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH	4
2.1. SYSTEM MAPPING	5
2.2. SYSTEM ANALYSIS: IDENTIFYING NEXUS CHALLENGES	5
2.3. TRANSITION TO STOCK-AND-FLOW DIAGRAM (SFD)	6
2.4. SFD VALIDATION.....	6
2.5. LEVERAGE POINTS DETECTION AND ANALYSIS	7
2.6. POLICY INTERVENTION DEFINITION	8
3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS	9
REFERENCES	12

Glossary of terms and abbreviations

Abbreviation / Term	Description
SES	Socio-Ecological System
PSDM	Participatory System Dynamic Modelling
SDM	System Dynamic Model
CLD	Causal Loop Diagram
SFD	Stock and Flow Diagram
LTM	Loop that Matter analysis
BCS	Biodiversity-Climate-Society Nexus

ABSTRACT

This work describes the activities carried out within BIOTRAILS project to develop and implement a Participatory System Dynamics approach for mapping and analysing the Biodiversity–Climate–Society Nexus. Specifically, the main goal of this work is to synthesise and critically analyse the experiences gained in the BIOTRAILS value chains related to the Participatory System Dynamic Modelling (PSDM) exercises, drawing on the lessons learned. A significant of this work describes the Stock and Flow Diagram (SFD) development, the quantitative system dynamic model used to co-design policy interventions and simulate scenarios.

1. INTRODUCTION

The accelerating pace of social and environmental change requires systemic approaches for sustainable resource management, recognizing the deep interconnections between society and ecology. The socio-ecological system (SES) concept frames these as complex, adaptive systems with feedbacks and emergent behaviors, while the Nexus approach applies systems thinking to highlight interdependencies among components such as biodiversity, climate, and society. The Biodiversity–Climate–Society (BCS) Nexus, in particular, illustrates how biodiversity loss, climate change, and societal well-being are tightly linked, with impacts and feedbacks that cross domains. Despite its conceptual appeal, the Nexus approach faces criticism for being difficult to operationalize in policy due to its complexity and the need for interdisciplinary collaboration. System Dynamic Modelling (SDM), especially through Causal Loop Diagrams (CLDs), helps visualize feedbacks and identify leverage points for intervention, but CLDs lack the ability to simulate time-dependent scenarios. Transitioning to quantitative Stock-and-Flow Diagrams (SFDs) addresses this gap, enabling dynamic simulation and more robust policy analysis. However, this transition introduces challenges: translating qualitative stakeholder knowledge into mathematical relationships can lead to loss of nuance, simplification may exclude important variables, and the complexity of SFDs can reduce stakeholder understanding and trust. These issues can hinder the identification and acceptance of effective leverage points for policy design [1; 2; 3; 4].

This work addresses these methodological challenges by comparing leverage points identified through qualitative (CLD) and quantitative (SFD) analyses, and by exploring their implications for designing impactful interventions within the BCS Nexus.

2. PSDM METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The BIOTRAILS PSDM approach integrates stakeholder knowledge with scientific data to support sustainable policy design. The methodology is structured in several phases, starting with qualitative mapping and progressing to quantitative simulation. Stakeholder engagement is central to the process through semi-structured interviews and participatory workshops. This collaborative process ensures that diverse perspectives are embedded in the system model, enhancing its relevance and credibility.

Figure 1: BIOTRAILS PSDM methodological framework

The different phases of the PSDM methodological approach are described in the following.

2.1. SYSTEM MAPPING

This phase involves creating a CLD to represent the relationships among different variables within the system visually. The CLD is developed through a participatory process that involves semi-structured interviews and workshops with stakeholders. The arrows in the diagram indicate cause-and-effect relationships, and the symbols at the end of the arrows (+ or -) show if the effect is reinforcing (positive feedback loop) or balancing (negative feedback loop). The CLD serves as a qualitative map to understand the system's structure and behaviour, including identifying feedback loops that drive change [5].

Figure 2 The causal connections influencing the deforestation process

2.2. SYSTEM ANALYSIS: IDENTIFYING NEXUS CHALLENGES

To move from a qualitative understanding to a more focused analysis, the methodology uses graph theory measures to analyze the CLD. By applying metrics like degree centrality (how connected a variable is), betweenness (how often a variable lies on the shortest path between others), and closeness (how easily a variable can reach others), the most influential variables in the system are

identified [6]. These key variables, especially those that cut across multiple sectors (biodiversity, climate, society), are defined as Nexus challenges. These challenges become the core focus for the next steps of the model.

2.3. TRANSITION TO STOCK-AND-FLOW DIAGRAM (SFD)

The process of developing a quantitative SFD from a qualitative CLD is a crucial step in the methodology. It begins by identifying the key BCS Nexus challenges from the CLD and coding them as stock variables in the SFD. A stock variable represents a quantity that can accumulate or deplete over time, capturing the state of the system. The Kumu platform's capabilities are used to isolate the causal connections of a specific variable from the CLD, which helps in identifying the elements that affect a stock's inflow (increase) and outflow (decrease) [1; 7; 8].

Once these influential elements are selected, they must be represented by mathematical equations in the SFD. The choice of equation is informed by several sources:

- **Historical Data:** Time-series data can help determine the past behaviour of variables.
- **Existing Literature:** Established models in relevant fields provide insights into typical mathematical representations.
- **Expert Knowledge:** Modellers' expertise in system dynamics is crucial for formulating appropriate equations.
- **Stakeholder Validation:** Stakeholder input is vital for refining the equations and ensuring they align with real-world understanding.

The expected dynamic behaviour of the stock variable over time—such as linear, exponential, logistic, or oscillatory patterns—plays a key role in selecting the most suitable mathematical formula. The initial equations are defined based on the modellers' understanding of the system's structure and are subsequently refined through a stakeholder-based validation phase.

The BIOTRAILS SFD was designed as a transdisciplinary tool. This means its quantification process was a synergistic integration of various knowledge sources beyond just stakeholder input. For example, parameters and initial values might have been informed by quantitative findings from EEMRIO/LCA analysis, while relationships for climate variables could have been based on Climate Projections. Additionally, insights from Structural Equation Models (SEM) could have informed the strength and direction of relationships between social, economic, and environmental variables, helping to translate statistical correlations into dynamic model relationships.

2.4. SFD VALIDATION

The validation of the SFD is a critical, collaborative step in the methodology, moving beyond a purely technical exercise to leverage the extensive knowledge of stakeholders. This approach ensures the model is grounded in real-world insights and practical experience [1; 7; 9].

To manage the complexity of the SFD, the validation process focuses on the key BCS Nexus challenges. The Behaviour-Over-Time (BOT) approach is used for this purpose. It involves visualizing and discussing how key variables behave over time, which helps to validate and refine the model's dynamics.

In a key phase of the validation, participants were asked to draw the expected evolution of the Nexus challenges on a two-axis graph for a 20-year period, divided into short-, mid-, and long-term steps. The discussion began with a Business-As-Usual (BAU) scenario, where participants described the expected changes (e.g., increase, decrease, stability) and their nature (e.g., rapid, slow, linear, fluctuating). To facilitate this, graphical representations of common dynamic behaviors or archetypes—such as linear change, exponential change, plateau, oscillation, and decline and recovery—were used.

Following the BAU scenario, stakeholders were asked to draw the expected evolution for both the most desirable and most undesirable scenarios. This resulted in three distinct graphs for each

challenge. The final validation step involved comparing these stakeholder-drawn graphs with the graphs obtained from the SFD's simulation. If a mismatch occurred, it signalled the need to revise the model's mathematical formulations. This iterative process ensured the model accurately reflected stakeholder understanding [9; 10].

Figure 3 Deforestation process in the SFD

2.5. LEVERAGE POINTS DETECTION AND ANALYSIS

Leverage points are critical junctures within a complex system where a small shift can lead to significant, transformative changes. The PSDM approach within the BIOTRAILS project focuses on identifying and analysing these points by shifting the focus from single variables to the underlying feedback loops that drive system behaviour. This approach ensures that interventions are not isolated but are part of a broader strategy for transformative change, particularly within the BCS Nexus [3; 4].

The methodology used for detecting leverage points in the BIOTRAILS project is a modified version of the "Loop That Matters" (LTM) method. While the original LTM method analyses the entire system, this approach is tailored to focus on specific BCS Nexus challenges, which are coded as stock variables in the SFD. This allows for a targeted evaluation of their dynamic evolution and the effectiveness of potential interventions [3; 4; 11; 12].

The process involves the following steps:

- **Identify the Target Variable:** The analysis begins by clearly defining the specific stock variable—one of the BCS Nexus challenges—that you want to influence.
- **Define the Impact Pathways:** Using the SFD structure, the causal pathways that directly or indirectly influence the target variable are traced. This involves identifying the feedback loops that connect the target variable to other elements in the system.
- **Calculate Link Scores:** The software STELLA is used to calculate "link scores" for each connection within the impact pathways. The link score quantifies the contribution and polarity of one variable to the change in another over time. This temporal dimension is crucial because the influence of feedback loops can change at different time steps.

- Calculate Pathway Strength: By qualitatively aggregating the link scores, the strength of each impact pathway is determined. The pathways with the strongest impact on the target variable are then used to identify potential leverage points.
- Visualise Loop Dominance: The method allows for the visualisation of how loop dominance changes over time. This helps to identify periods when specific loops become particularly influential, highlighting critical moments for interventions.
- Understand Loop Interaction: Although the analysis initially isolates loops for each Nexus challenge, it is recognised that these loops are interconnected. Therefore, effective leverage point design requires understanding how changes in one loop might affect the entire system.
- Scenario Testing: The SFD allows for scenario testing by simulating different interventions and observing their impact on the target variable, which helps in optimising interventions and understanding synergies and trade-offs.

This modified LTM approach provides a practical framework for identifying and implementing interventions that lead to meaningful and sustainable changes by focusing on the core mechanisms of the system's behaviour over time.

Figure 4 Impact Pathway affecting the degradation rate

2.6 POLICY INTERVENTION DEFINITION

The identification of leverage points through the revised LTM approach is a crucial step for co-designing policy interventions within the BCS Nexus. By pinpointing areas where small changes can lead to significant impacts, the framework allows policymakers to focus on effective interventions that address the underlying structures driving undesirable outcomes, rather than just treating symptoms. This ensures efficient use of limited resources and maximises impact [3; 4].

A key output of this phase is the identification of "windows of opportunity"—periods during which certain actions will be most effective. This is achieved by analysing the dynamic evolution of the

feedback loops that influence leverage points, as their impact can change over time [3; 4]. The process of defining a "desirable outcome" is both normative and participatory, involving stakeholders in defining system goals and managing conflicting interests [3; 4; 9; 10; 13]. This can be done through methods like multi-criteria decision analysis, negotiation, and scenario planning. The BIOTRAILS framework integrates the leverage points identified through this dynamic analysis with those from other project tasks, ensuring a robust and comprehensive understanding of intervention opportunities.

It's important to note that this framework provides a crucial scientific foundation for policy recommendations by highlighting key intervention points and potential consequences, but it does not constitute the policy design process itself, which involves political, legal, and implementation considerations. The results of this work will be presented in a final round of stakeholder workshops.

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

1. Main challenges in engaging stakeholders in SDM development

Engaging stakeholders throughout the PSDM process is crucial for ensuring that the model reflects diverse perspectives and incorporates contextual knowledge. However, several challenges were encountered:

Complexity of CLDs: The initial CLDs developed with stakeholders were often too complex for subsequent analysis and SFD development. Simplification was necessary, but it was not always feasible to involve stakeholders in this process, potentially affecting the model's adherence to their knowledge. We tried to reduce this risk by involving the case study leaders in the CLD revision process and validating the obtained CLD with the stakeholders.

Trust and transparency: The transition from CLD to SFD is crucial for supporting the design of Nexus policy interventions. However, stakeholders may perceive the SFD as a "black box" due to its complexity, which can hinder their engagement and understanding. This lack of transparency can negatively affect trust and reduce the model's usability for policy design. To overcome this limit, the SFD was validated by engaging stakeholders. Moreover, the Stella interface for simulating the intervention scenarios will be tested by key stakeholders before being used during the policy design workshop. This testing phase will be carried out before September.

Knowledge translation: Translating stakeholders' contextual knowledge into formal mathematical relationships in the SFD can be difficult. Some knowledge may be lost in the quantification process, potentially overlooking leverage points considered important by stakeholders. To overcome this limit, the SFD validation allowed us to assess to what extent the mathematical formalisation of the causal connection in the SFD was capable of accounting for the stakeholders' knowledge and perception.

2. Comparing qualitative and quantitative leverage points detection and analysis

The BIOTRAILS project utilises a system dynamics approach to leverage points detection, focusing on feedback loop analysis. This approach, based on the Loops That Matter (LTM) method, differs from simply addressing isolated components by emphasising the system's underlying structure and the influence of feedback loops over time.

Qualitative analysis (CLD): CLDs provide a visual representation of causal relationships and are useful for identifying reinforcing and balancing loops. However, they lack the time dimension necessary for scenario testing and policy impact modelling.

Quantitative analysis (SFD): SFDs enable quantitative simulations and policy impact modelling, providing a more structured representation for evidence-based nexus policy design. The LTM method, adapted in BIOTRAILS, focuses on identifying the most influential feedback loops affecting target variables, such as BCS nexus challenges. An important innovation was introduced in the LTM implementation in BIOTRAILS, allowing a focus on the loop dominance analysis on the

BCS Nexus challenges.

3. Key lessons from the Nexus policy design

The application of the PSDM approach in BIOTRAILS has yielded valuable lessons for nexus policy design:

- Context-specific solutions: The case studies highlight the need for context-specific policy interventions. For example, in the Gold Mining value chain in Ghana, leverage points for addressing soil and land degradation include local community awareness and institutional capacity. In contrast, the Handicraft value chain in the Amazon forest requires policies that promote the handicraft sector to protect biodiversity by preventing depopulation and deforestation.
- Importance of multi-sectoral analysis: Nexus challenges span multiple sectors, necessitating interventions that address the interconnected nature of these challenges. The BIOTRAILS approach emphasizes the importance of considering the multi-sectoral impact of central elements in the system to ensure effective interventions.
- Dynamic approach to leverage points: The influence of feedback loops and, consequently, the effectiveness of leverage points can change over time. Therefore, an adaptive approach is necessary, where leverage points are reassessed and adjusted based on the system dynamics.
- Integration with existing policy structures: Effective policy design requires a thorough understanding of the current policy environment. The PSDM work intersects with this by:
 - Identifying policy gaps: The analysis of leverage points and system dynamics can reveal areas where current policies are insufficient or misaligned to address Nexus challenges.
 - Identify policy resistance mechanisms: PSDM could help identify elements in the system hampering/delaying the implementation of specific policies.
 - Informing policy coherence: The multi-sectoral perspective helps ensure that new policies are coherent with existing ones across different sectors, minimising unintended negative consequences.
 - Providing a framework for policy evaluation: The dynamic approach allows for the development of policies that can be monitored and adapted as the system evolves and the effectiveness of existing policies can be evaluated.

4. Main limitation of the BIOTRAILS PSDM approach

While the BIOTRAILS PSDM approach offers a valuable framework for analysing and managing Nexus challenges, it's important to acknowledge its inherent limitations:

- Stakeholder Bias: The reliance on stakeholder input, while crucial for incorporating local knowledge and ensuring relevance, introduces the potential for bias. The selection of participants can influence the perspectives represented, and dominant voices may overshadow marginalised ones. Therefore, the results should be interpreted as reflecting the understanding of the specific group of stakeholders involved, and it is acknowledged that different participants might yield different insights.
- Subjectivity in Knowledge Elicitation: The process of translating stakeholder knowledge into CLDs and SFDs involves a degree of subjectivity. Modellers' interpretations and choices in formalising relationships can influence the model's structure and outcomes. While validation efforts mitigate this, some knowledge loss or distortion is inevitable.
- Data Availability and Validation: The availability and quality of quantitative data to validate and parameterise SFDs can be a limiting factor. In some cases, stakeholder perceptions may not be fully corroborated by empirical data, highlighting the need for careful triangulation of information where possible.

- **Generalizability:** The case study-based approach, while providing context-specific insights, may limit the generalizability of findings. The transferability of leverage points and policy recommendations to other contexts should be considered cautiously, requiring adaptation to specific social-ecological conditions.

It is important to consider these limitations when interpreting the results of the BIOTRAILS PSDM framework. Further research could focus on quantifying the degree of bias and uncertainty introduced through stakeholder engagement and knowledge elicitation, as well as developing strategies to integrate stakeholder knowledge with quantitative data in a more robust manner.

The work described in this document is not yet completed. The next steps involve the finalisation of the SFD in the two remaining case studies – i.e. the cocoa production in Perù and the Fishery and Aquaculture in Greece.

In conclusion, the BIOTRAILS project has laid a strong foundation for using PSDM to address the complex interdependencies within the BCS Nexus. The lessons learned and the methodological advancements made will be invaluable for future efforts to promote sustainable and transformative changes across various sectors and regions.

REFERENCES

1. Sterman, J. (2000). *Business Dynamics, System Thinking and Modeling for a Complex World*. McGraw-Hill.
2. Videira, N., Schneider, F., Sekulova, F., & Kallis, G. (2014). Improving understanding on degrowth pathways: An exploratory study using collaborative causal models. *Futures*, 55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2013.11.001>
3. Abson, D. J., Fischer, J., Leventon, J., Newig, J., & Vilsmaier, U. (2017). Leverage points for sustainability transformation. *Ambio*, 46(1), 30–39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-016-0800-y>
4. Cebrià-Piqueras, M. A., Karrasch, L., & Wirth, C. (2023). Leverage points for transformative change in social-ecological systems. *Ecology and Society*, 28(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-12856-280101>
5. Haraldsson, H. "Developing methods for modelling procedures in System Analysis and System Dynamics." Lund University, 2005.
6. Freeman, L. C. "A Set of Measures of Centrality Based on Betweenness." *Sociometry*, vol. 40, no. 1, 1977, pp. 35–41.
7. Cavana, R. Y., & Maani, K. E. (2004). A methodology for system dynamics modeling of complex business systems. *System Dynamics Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sdr.294>
8. Elias, A. A. (2012). System dynamics modeling for sustainability. In *System Dynamics Modeling for Sustainability*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-78912-2_4
9. Braun, W. (2002). The system archetypes. In *The System Archetypes*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-78912-2_2
10. Ison, R. (2008). Systems thinking and practice for action research. In *Handbook of Action Research*. Sage Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781848607934.n17>
11. Schoenberg, W., Davidsen, P., & Eberlein, R. (2020). Understanding model behavior using the Loops that Matter method. *System Dynamics Review*, 36(2), 158–190. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sdr.1658>
12. Hayward, J., & Roach, P. A. (2024). A comparison of loop dominance methods: measures and meaning. *System Dynamics Review*, 40(2), e1757.
13. Giordano, R., Osann, A., Henao, E., López, M. L., Piqueras, J. G., Nikolaidis, N. P., Lilli, M., Coletta, V. R., & Pagano, A. (2025). Causal Loop Diagrams for bridging the gap between Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem Nexus thinking and Nexus doing. *Journal of Hydrology*, 650, 132571. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2024.132571>